

THE DEFECT FORMED AFTER 60 DAYS AFTER SURGERY IN THE CONTROL GROUP.

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Annotation.

Improvement of methods of diagnostics and treatment of concomitant traumas of the maxillofacial region should be aimed at improving the quality of diagnosis for more accurate planning of surgery, reduction of traumatization during surgery, acceleration of rehabilitation period.

Key words.

traumas of maxillofacial region, combined traumas, maxillofacial surgery

3.6. Morphological examination results.

On the 7th day of the experiment, the morphological study of the dynamics of reparative regeneration of bone tissue in the area of the artificially created defect in the mandible in the animals of the control group showed that the area of the defect is filled with a blood clot and around it, osteogenic tissue with the formation of primary bone structures is observed. During this period, osteoplastic material "OsteonTM II Collagen" is used in the area of the defect due to blood vessels growing into the drug from the surrounding bone tissue, and its entry into a soft and porous structure is observed.

Fig. 1 After 7 days of the experiment (control). Filling the area of the formed defect with a blood clot. Osteogenic tissue is detected around. Hematoxylin-eosin. Mass.: x400

2. Fig. From 7 days of experience (basic). Blood vessels growing into a bone graft. Hematoxylin-eosin. Mass.:x200

On the 14th day of the experiment, in the control group of animals, in the area of the bone defect filled with blood clot, a thin connective tissue appears in the form of a mesh, collagen is located between fibroblast fibers and individual vessels. The process of bone formation is not observed. In animals of the experimental group, primary bone trabeculae surrounded by osteoblasts are observed around the blood vessels during this research period. The transplant area is surrounded by bone tissue, the space between the beams is filled with blood vessels covered with endothelium and osteoblasts.

On the 21st day of the experiment, an ossification zone in the form of immature bone beams was found in the control group. Blood vessels and osteoblasts are located in the interstices of the beam. During this period of the experiment, the intensive process of osteogenesis continues in the main group of animals. Bone beams are larger and are also found around blood vessels. A decrease in the size of the deposited bone material is determined.

Fig. 3. After 14 days of the experiment (control). Thin connective tissue at the site of a blood clot. Hematoxylin-eosin. Mass.:x200.

Fig. 4. After 14 days of experiment (main). Bony beams between blood vessels. Hematoxylin-eosin. Mass.:x200

On the 30th day of the experiment, it is clear that the process of osteogenesis in the main group of animals is more advanced than in the control group. Osteoplastic material is gradually replaced by bone tissue. The area of the bone defect is filled

with relatively dense bone tissue, in some places compact bone formation in the form of thin bone plates is detected. This situation is not observed in the control group.

Figure 5 21 days after the experiment (control). Thin bony beams surround the blood vessels. Hematoxylin-eosin. Mass.:x200

Fig. 6. After the 30th day of the experiment (main). Compact bone tissue forming in the form of soft bone beams. Hematoxylin-eosin. Mass.:x400

After two months of the experiment, bone plates and bone beams were observed in the defect area in the control animals. In some places, bone tissue looks like thin bone beams, in some places it looks like bone plates. This indicates the continuation of the process of transformation of rough fibrous bone tissue into

lamellar tissue. In the main group of animals of the experiment, a bone mass in the form of lamellar bone tissue typical for the lower jaw was formed in place of the osteograft used in the area of the defect during this period of the study. The transplant area is combined with bone tissue, the borders of the previous defect are not defined.

Fig. 7 After 60 days of experience (basic). Bone plate covered with porous connective tissue and blood vessels. Hematoxylin-eosin. Mass.:x200

Fig. 8 After 60 days of the experiment (control). Alternating formation of bony beams and (red indicator) soft bone plates (yellow indicator). Hematoxylin-eosin. Mass: x.200

Acceleration of the bone tissue regeneration process is observed after the use of composite bone material and osteoplastic material created on the basis of natural (bovine) type I collagen in an artificially created defect in the lower jaw bone tissue. The presence of collagen in the composition makes the material soft and porous, shortens the total time of the operation, and facilitates application. Bone grafting has shown good results in attaching to the surface of bone trabeculae by activating osteoblasts, which accelerates the formation of bone plates. The increase in the activity of osteoblasts is determined by the initiation of the revascularization mechanism, the increase in the secretion of carbohydrates, growth factors, protein and mineral components of the bone.

LIST OF LITERATURE:

1. Alimurodovich, Khalikov Azizbek, and Rakhmatov Jakhongir Bakhodirovich. "COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF MFR PLASTIC OPERATIONS." *American Journal of Technology and Applied Sciences* 7 (2022): 34-38.
2. Фаттаева, Д. Р., Ризаев, Ж. А., Рахимова, Д. А., & Холиков, А. А. (2021). CLINICAL PICTURE OF SINUSITIS IN PATIENTS AFTER COVID-19 WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE. *ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ*, 2(2).
3. Urunbaeva, S. S., Alishakhi, L. S., Pirmatov, M. A., & Fattayeva, D. R. (2022). OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH PHLEGMON OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION. *British View*, 7(4).
4. Mamadrizaeva, Z. F., Rakhmatova, S. S., Yunusov, A. A., & Fattayeva, D. R. (2022). FEATURES OF THE TREATMENT OF FRACTURES OF THE ZYGOMATIC-ORBITAL COMPLEX. *British View*, 7(4).
5. Urunbaeva, S. S., Pirmatov, M. A., Nosirov, S. S., & Kholikov, A. A. (2022). COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TREATMENT OF MANDIBULAR FRACTURES. *British View*, 7(4).
6. Olimjonov, T. A., Fattayeva, D. R., & Umarov, J. A. (2022). Treatment methods for fractures of the zygomatic-orbital complex. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 13, 65-68.
7. Shamov, V. V., Kholikov, A. A., & Fattayeva, D. R. (2022). Improvement of treatment methods of combined traumas of maxillofacial region. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 13, 56-61.

8. Холмурадов, Ж. Р., Холиков, А. А., & Фаттаева, Д. Р. (2022). МЕТОДЫ ОБСЛЕДОВАНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ С ФЛЕГМОНАМИ ЧЕЛЮСТНОЛИЦЕВОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(12), 97-101.

9. Alimurodovich, K. A., & Rustamovna, F. D. (2023). Differential Diagnosis of Facial Pain. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(4), 36-42.